

Benzocoumarin as a potential scaffold:

A review of its biomedical activities

La benzocumarina como andamio potencial: una revisión de sus actividades biomédicas

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Abstract

Coumarin derivatives have piqued the curiosity of many researchers in the medicine and industry fields due primarily to their chemical diversity and bioactivities. Amongst coumarin derivatives, benzocoumarins have garnered significant interest from pharmaceutical chemists in the past few years. Many scientific studies in the literature reported the bioactivities of natural and synthesized benzocoumarin derivatives. The focus of this review was on the general synthetic routes of benzocoumarins, besides the depiction of their biological activities, particularly those pertaining to anticancer, antioxidant, antibacterial, antiviral, and antidiabetic potentials. The authors concluded that the benzocoumarin backbone is an attractive scaffold that sheds light on exploring new drug candidates with novel or improved bioactivities.

Keywords: Benzocoumarin, Antitumor, Antioxidant, Antibacterial, Antifungal, Antidiabetic.

Resumen

Los derivados de la cumarina han despertado la curiosidad de muchos investigadores en los campos de la medicina y la industria debido principalmente a su diversidad química y bioactividades. Entre los derivados de la cumarina, las benzocoumarinas han despertado un gran interés entre los químicos farmacéuticos en los últimos años. Muchos estudios científicos en la literatura informaron sobre las bioactividades de los derivados de benzocoumarina naturales y sintetizados. El enfoque de esta revisión estuvo en las rutas sintéticas generales de las benzocoumarinas, además de la descripción de sus actividades biológicas, particularmente aquellas relacionadas con los potenciales anticancerígenos, antioxidantes, antibacterianos, antivirales y antidiabéticos. Los autores concluyeron que la columna vertebral de la benzocoumarina es un andamio atractivo que arroja luz sobre la exploración de nuevos fármacos candidatos con bioactividades novedosas o mejoradas.

Palabras clave: Benzocoumarina, Antitumoral, Antioxidante, Antibacteriano, Antifúngico, Antidiabético.

Introduction

Coumarin (also known as 2*H*-chromen-2-one) is an organic compound that belongs to the chemical class known as benzopyrone^{1,2}. Coumarin and its derivatives constitute a large group of natural and synthetic compounds with different biological effects such as anticancer³⁻⁸, antioxidant⁹⁻¹², antimicrobial¹³⁻¹⁷, anticoagulants¹⁸, anti-inflammatory¹⁹⁻²¹. Furthermore, chemists are interested in them because of their variety of applications, such as photosensitizers²², optical brighteners²³, laser and fluorescent dyes²⁴, and as additives in cosmetics, perfumes, food, and pharmaceuticals²⁵. Numerous molecules based on the coumarin backbone structure were synthesized using novel synthetic techniques²⁶.

Benzocoumarins (benzochromenones) are benzene-fused coumarins that belong to the π -extended coumarins class. In the parent coumarin backbone **S1**, the position of the fused aromatic ring categorizes benzocoumarin derivatives into four types: benzo[*h*]coumarin **S2** (7,8-benzocoumarin), benzo[*g*]coumarin **S3** (6,7-benzocoumarin), benzo[*f*]coumarin **S4** (5,6-benzocoumarin), and benzo[*c*]coumarin **S5** (3,4-benzocoumarin), as shown in Figure 1²⁷.

In the past few years, several benzocoumarin-based compounds have been widely synthesized, and their bioactivities prompted efforts to explore new therapeutic agents²⁸. These findings provoked the research team to publish a review on the well-known synthetic strategies to prepare benzocoumarins, along with the pharmacological potentials of synthetic and natural benzocoumarins, concentrating on the most significant examples.

Figure 1. The chemical backbone of coumarin and benzocoumarins.

Synthetic methods of benzocoumarins

Except for the benzo[*c*]coumarins, benzocoumarin derivatives are synthesized using the same methods as coumarin and its derivatives, such as metal-catalyzed cyclization²⁹, Pechmann reaction³⁰, and Knoevenagel condensation³¹. Nearly all of these synthetic routes begin with one of two groups of chemical compounds: naphthols or *o*-hydroxynaphthaldehyde. The 2*H*-chromen-2-one moiety

is synthesized from *o*-hydroxynaphthaldehyde through intramolecular cyclization with the hydroxyl group after initial Knoevenagel condensation with a malonate ester or analogs, as indicated in Scheme 1³². The positions of hydroxyl and formyl groups on the initial *o*-hydroxynaphthaldehyde compounds determine the creation of different types of benzocoumarin derivatives (1-hydroxy-2-naphthaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde)³³.

Scheme 1. General strategy of benzocoumarins synthesis from *o*-hydroxynaphthaldehydes.

On the other hand, by electrophilic substitution of naphthol compounds with β -keto esters followed by intramolecular cyclization process, benzocoumarins can be directly synthesized (the upper pathway in Scheme 2). In the presence of a strong Lewis acid or Bronsted acid as a catalyst, the reaction occurs with suitable electrophiles. Additionally, functionalization of aryl C-H of alkynoate compounds by using metal as a catalyst is also possible, as illustrated in Scheme 2²⁷. The position of the hydroxyl group in the initial naphthol compounds (1-naphthol or 2-naphthol) also influences the formation of various types of benzocoumarin-based derivatives. Two isomers form in significant amounts from 2-naphthol, and their polarity differences allow them to be separated³³. Many synthetic methods for benzo[*f*], benzo[*h*], and benzo[*g*]coumarins have been developed based on the two general strategies mentioned above.

Scheme 2. General strategy of benzocoumarins synthesis from naphthols.

Symbol	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	Product
S2	-H	-H	-CH=CH-CH=CH-	-H	Benzo[<i>h</i>]coumarin
S3	-H	-CH=CH-CH=CH-	-H	-H	Benzo[<i>g</i>]coumarin
S4	-CH=CH-CH=CH-	-H	-H	-H	Benzo[<i>f</i>]coumarin

Benzo[*c*]coumarin **S5** synthesis takes a slightly different approach. There are various reactions for synthesizing benzo[*c*] coumarins. These reactions are classified into the following categories: (A) ring-closing reactions: (1) the carbon-carbon bond formation; (2) the carbon-oxygen bond formation; (3) cyclization reactions. (B) ring-transformation reactions: (1) specific oxidation; (2) aromatization; (3) ring enlargement³³.

Biomedical activities of benzocoumarin-based compounds

Benzocoumarins have immense interest due to their prominent pharmacological activities, such as antidyslipidemic³⁴, antioxidant³⁵, antimicrobial³⁶, and cytotoxic effects³⁷. In laboratory assays, numerous benzocoumarin containing compounds, either from the natural or synthetic origin, were evaluated for their biological actions²⁸. This section will cover the bioactivities of many synthesized and natural benzocoumarin-based derivatives, besides the development of structurally-related analogs with novel or enhanced bioactivities, and highlight the most important molecular and structural factors that influence the activities.

Antitumor biomedical activity

Tan and his colleagues have reported the anticancer activity of two novel benzocoumarin-based products, graphislactone H (**S6**) and graphislactone G (**S7**), in addition to previously known products, alternariol monomethyl ether (**S8**) and graphislactone A (**S9**), as shown in Figure 2. These products were isolated from *Cephalosporium acremonium* IFB-E007 and showed a significant inhibitory action versus SW1116 cell lines, with IC₅₀ values of 12, 21, 14, and 8.5 µg/ml, respectively³⁸.

Figure 2. Benzo[*c*]coumarin-based products with antitumor activity reported by Tan et al.

Tanshinlactone A (**S10**), as illustrated in Figure 3, was extracted from *Salvia miltiorrhiza* root by Don and his colleagues. This natural product exhibited moderate cytotoxicity with IC₅₀ values ranging from 6.87 to 8.85 µg/ml versus the test cell lines, which included OVCAR-3 (ovarian adenocarcinoma), HepG2 (hepatocellular carcinoma), and HeLa (cervical epithelioid carcinoma)³⁹.

Figure 3. Benzo[*h*]coumarin-based product with antitumor activity reported by Don et al.

In 2000, bioassay-directed fractionation was used to isolate Vismiaguianins A (**S11**) and B (**S12**) from the *Vismia guianensis* roots, as indicated in Figure 4. Compound **S11**, which had a dimethylpyran ring, was cytotoxic versus KB cells. While compound **S12**, which had a dihydrofuran ring bearing a hydroxyisopropyl group, was inactive. The authors concluded that a dimethylpyran ring in the backbone of **S11** is important for cytotoxicity⁴⁰.

Figure 4. Benzo[*h*]coumarin-based products with antitumor activity as depicted by Seo et al.

Also, in 2004 Lee and his colleagues isolated *neo*-tanshinlactone (**S13**) from the *Salvia miltiorrhiza* roots, as demonstrated in Figure 5. This natural product exhibited marked suppression versus two estrogen receptor-positive human breast cancer cell lines, which are 20-fold more selective and 10-fold more potent than tamoxifen. Also, the product **S13** was potent in inhibiting human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 overexpression and estrogen receptor-negative breast cancer cell lines. Among the naturally isolated benzocoumarins, **S13** has been identified as a promising lead compound for the development of innovative anti-breast cancer medicines⁴¹.

Figure 5. Benzo[*h*]coumarin-based product with antitumor activity described by Lee et al.

In continuing research, Lee and his colleagues have investigated the structure-activity relationship of a series of synthesized analogs of **S13**, as illustrated in Figure 6. Analogs that contain a methyl-substituted furan ring exhibited greater cytotoxicity than those with hydroxy dihydrofuran or unsubstituted furan rings. However, those without a furan ring did not demonstrate good activity. Compound **S14** showed excellent selectivity and activity versus HS 587-1 (ER-), MDA MB-231, ZR-75-1 (ER+), and MCF-7 cell lines. Moreover, compound **S14** demonstrated high potency versus SK-BR-3 (HER2+, ER-) cell lines⁴².

Similarly, other analogs as anti-breast cancer drugs were discovered through similar research, including **S15-S19**, as shown in Figure 6. Compound **S15** was more selective versus ZR-75-1 than MCF-7 cells, whereas **S16** demonstrated a selectivity ratio of about 12-fold for SK-BR-3/MCF-7 cells. Compound **S17** exhibited higher potency versus ZR-75-1 and SK-BR-3 cell lines than compound **S13**⁴³. Based on the structure of **S13**, compounds **S18** and **S19** were designed as new scaffolds with secondary amine substituents. When compared to **S13**, they both had broader antitumor activities. The structure-activity relationship data showed that the nitrogen substitutions were important for cytotoxic potency⁴⁴.

In addition, Lee and his colleagues investigated the amino-substituted analogs that are water-soluble, yielding an active novel benzo[*h*]coumarin-based compound **S20**. Compared with the preceding lead compound **S18**, compound **S20** had a 50-fold increase in water solubility. In mutant mice, the branching of the mammary gland and the total number of mammary cells were reduced by the compounds **S18** and **S20**. Also, one-week therapy with **S20** reduced bromodeoxyuridine-positive cells in mammary glands that are prone to malignancy by 80%⁴⁵.

Figure 6. Chemical backbones of neo-tanshinlactone (**S13**) synthesized analogs described by Lee et al.

In 2010, Konwar and his colleagues conducted a study inspired by a neo-tanshinlactone scaffold. This study included the development of a series of new benzocoumarins (**S21-S23**), as demonstrated in Figure 7, on the basis of naturally developed neo-tanshinlactone (**S13**) and assessment of their cytotoxicity versus MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7 breast cancer cell lines. The proliferation of MCF-7 cancerous cells line was strongly suppressed by compounds **S21-S23** which

had IC_{50} values of 3.8, 6.5, and 7.9 μ M, respectively. These compounds were able to evoke caspase-dependent death, cell-cycle arrest, and nuclear fragmentation in MCF-7 cells line while being non-cytotoxic to normal osteoblast cells⁴⁶.

Figure 7. Benzo[*h*]coumarin-based compounds with antitumor activity synthesized by Konwar et al.

Recently, Al-Masoudi and his colleagues reported the synthesis of novel benzo[*f*]coumarin-based arylamide analogs and benzo[*f*]coumarin-chalcone with aryl ester derivatives. The antitumor activities of these compounds were evaluated versus human prostate cancer cells line (PC-3). The new compounds **S24** and **S25**, with IC_{50} values of 78.25 and 71.35 μ g/mL, respectively, were the most active cytotoxic analogs in the series, as shown in Figure 8⁴⁷.

Figure 8. Benzo[*f*]coumarin-based compounds with antitumor activity prepared by Al-Masoudi et al.

Antioxidant biomedical activity

Song and his colleagues have extracted graphisilactone A (**S9**) from the cultures of endophytes sheltered in *Trachelospermum jasminoides*, as illustrated in Figure 9. The authors found that the natural product **S9** revealed promising scavenging activities with an IC_{50} of 2.9 μ g/mL versus 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl free radicals. Also, it demonstrated more activities than butylated hydroxytoluene in removing hydroxyl radicals in a dose-related manner. Furthermore, compound **S9** exhibited better antioxidant activities than ascorbic acid in the antioxidant assay, in addition to suppressing reactive substances formation during LDL oxidation using Cu^{+2} as an oxidative inducer⁴⁸.

Figure 9. Benzo[*c*]coumarin-based product with antioxidant activity reported by Song et al.

Also, Ferreira and his colleagues evaluated the antioxidant activities of urolithins, which are produced from the metabolism of pomegranate ellagitannins by the gut microbiome. The research team used a cellular assay that permits the detection of antioxidant activity of the test compounds, besides estimation of their bioavailability in the cells. The assay estimated the ability of the tested urolithins to inhibit the oxidation of 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein by reactive oxygen species⁴⁹. As illustrated in Figure 10, urolithin C (**S28**) and urolithin D (**S29**) showed high antioxidative activities with IC₅₀ values of 0.16 and 0.33 μM, respectively, while urolithin A (**S26**) exhibited less antioxidative activities with IC₅₀ values of 13.6 μM. On the other hand, urolithin B (**S27**) and all methylated urolithins (**S30-S32**) did not have antioxidative activity. The authors concluded that the antioxidant activity of these benzocoumarins was related to the molecule's lipophilicity, as well as to the number of OH groups substituted on the molecule⁴⁹.

Figure 10. Chemical structures of benzo[c]coumarin-based urolithins.

Sashidhara and his colleagues have synthesized a series of Schiff bases using benzo[h]coumarin dicarbonyl as a building block and evaluated their antioxidant and lipid-lowering activities. As demonstrated in Figure 11, two of these synthesized benzocoumarin derivatives, herein termed **S33** and **S34**, possessed the most promising antioxidant and lipid-lowering activities among the others⁵⁰.

Figure 11. Benzo[h]coumarin-based compounds with antioxidant activity synthesized by Sashidhara et al.

In 2016, Salem and his colleagues reported the synthesis of novel series of coumarin- and benzocoumarin-based derivatives. These newly prepared compounds were examined to evaluate their antioxidant potential in tissue homogenates from rat brains and kidneys. As shown

in Figure 12, compounds **S37**, **S38**, **S42**, **S36**, and **S40** exhibited a high ability to inhibit oxidation, and the percentage of their inhibitions were 84.6, 84.6, 84.6, 84.4, and 84.4%, respectively. Compounds **S41**, **S35**, and **S44** exhibited high inhibition activities of 75.5, 72.9, and 69.3%, respectively, while compounds **S39**, **S43**, and **S45** showed moderate to weak inhibitions of 56.2, 51.9, and 43.1%, respectively. Furthermore, the authors concluded that the compounds with the benzocoumarin-based scaffold exhibited better antioxidant potential than their coumarin-based scaffold analogs⁵¹.

Figure 12. Benzo[f]coumarin-based compounds with antioxidant activity prepared by Salem et al.

Antibacterial biomedical activity

Kim and his colleagues have extracted and isolated novel benzo[c]coumarin dimers called verrulactones A (**S46**) and B (**S47**) from the culture media of *Penicillium verrucosum* F375 fungus. As shown in Figure 13, the natural products **S46** and **S47** exhibited antibacterial activity versus methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Also, they revealed strong inhibition of the enoyl-ACP reductase of *Staphylococcus aureus* in a concentration-dependent manner⁵².

Figure 13. Dimeric benzo[c]coumarin-based products with antibacterial activity reported by Kim et al.

In a separated study, Kamal El-Dean and his colleagues have reported the synthesis of a series of benzocoumarin-

based compounds attached with pyrazolyl, or oxadiazolyl, or thiazolidinyl moieties and evaluated their antibacterial properties. The synthesized compounds revealed intriguing structure-activity relationship. As demonstrated in Figure 14, all compounds numbered **S48-S58** exhibited remarkable activity versus all tested bacterial strains, except for compound **S50**, which had no or only weak antibacterial property⁵³.

Figure 14. Benzo[f]coumarin-based compounds with antibacterial activity prepared by Kamal El-Dean et al.

In 2018, Lin and his colleagues reported the antibacterial activity of dendrocoumarin (**S59**), a novel benzocoumarin-based product, and itolide A (**S60**), a previously known benzocoumarin-based product, as shown in Figure 15. These products were isolated from *Dendrobium nobile* stems and exhibited a promising antibacterial potential with broad-spectrum activity versus the test bacteria⁵⁴.

Figure 15. Benzo[c]coumarin-based products with antibacterial activity as depicted by Lin et al.

Recently, Patel and Patel synthesized and evaluated the antibacterial property of new naphthalene substituted benzocoumarin-based compounds. As illustrated in Figure 16, all the synthesized compounds **S61-S66** exhibited significant activity versus the test bacteria. Also, the authors concluded that compounds **S62** and **S65** that have OCH_3 group on the 8th position of the coumarin ring revealed the most promising antibacterial activity among the others⁵⁵.

Figure 16. Benzo[c]coumarin-based compounds with antibacterial activity prepared by Patel and Patel.

Antifungal biomedical activity

Zeng and his colleagues have isolated Itolide A (**S60**), a benzocoumarin-based product, for the first time from *Itoa orientalis* seeds. As shown in Figure 17, the natural product **S60** revealed weak antifungal activity versus the test fungi with IC_{50} values of 132.25 μM towards *Rhizoctonia solani* and 240.00 μM towards *Sclerotium rolfsii*⁵⁶.

Figure 17. Benzo[c]coumarin-based product with antifungal activity reported by Zeng et al.

In addition, Kamal El-Dean and his colleagues have evaluated the antifungal property of the synthesized series of benzocoumarin-based compounds (**S48-S58**), which are attached with pyrazolyl, or oxadiazolyl, or thiazolidinyl moieties, as illustrated in Figure 14. Some of these compounds exhibited remarkable activity towards the test fungi strains. For example, compound **S49** revealed significant activity versus all the test fungal strains, while compound **S48** had activity only versus *Fusarium oxysporum* fungi. Also, the best antifungal activity were attributed to compound **S55**, which had oxime moiety in its chemical backbone⁵³.

In 2020, Jaber and his colleagues reported the synthesis of novel series of benzocoumarin-based compounds attached with anti-inflammatory drugs through an alkyl amide linker, as shown in Figure 18. These newly prepared compounds (**S67-S73**) were screened to evaluate their antifungal property. The outcomes revealed that all these compounds

possessed significant activity versus the test fungal strains, but compounds **S67**, **S69**, and **S73** were the best ⁵⁷.

Figure 18. Benzo[f]coumarin-based compounds with antifungal activity synthesized by Jaber et al.

In a continuing study, Jaber and his colleagues have synthesized and evaluated the antifungal potential of new series of benzocoumarin-chalcone connected with anti-inflammatory drug moieties via an ester linker (**S74-S80**), as shown in Figure 19. Compounds **S74**, **S75**, **S76**, and **S78** revealed good antifungal activity towards the test fungi. The authors deduced that the NH, F, Cl, and methoxy groups play a specific role in this activity³⁷.

Figure 19. Benzo[f]coumarin-chalcone-based compounds with antifungal activity prepared by Jaber et al.

Antidiabetic biomedical activity

In 2015, Soman and Sharma reported the designing, synthesizing, and evaluating 3-aminocoumarin-based compounds as dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV) inhibitors to treat type II diabetes. Among all the synthesized compounds, the benzocoumarin-based compound **S81**, as illustrated in Figure 20, had the highest potency to inhibit DPP-IV enzyme activity with an IC_{50} value of 3.16 μ M. Furthermore, the docking studies revealed that the **S81** compound had the best affinity for binding to the enzyme than the other prepared compounds ⁵⁸.

Figure 20. Benzo[h]coumarin-based compound with antidiabetic potential prepared by Soman and Sharma.

In a specific study, Naveed and his colleagues have isolated two novel benzocoumarin-based products, longipetalasin A (**S82**) and B (**S83**), from *Tribulus longipetalus*, as shown in Figure 21. The authors found that the natural products **S82** and **S83** possessed an excellent inhibition of α -glucosidase enzyme activity with IC_{50} values of 94.17 and 85.65 μ M, respectively. Consequently, the authors proposed that these products are promising drug candidates for the management of diabetes mellitus ⁵⁹.

Figure 21. Benzo[g]coumarin-based products with antidiabetic potential described by Naveed et al.

In 2016, Imhoff and his colleagues have isolated three benzocoumarin-based compounds, alternariol-9-methyl ether (**S8**), alternariol (**S84**), and pannorin (**S85**), from *Aspergillus* and *Botryotinia fuckeliana* marine fungi, as illustrated in Figure 22. For the first time, these natural products showed efficient inhibition of the glycogen-synthase-kinase-3 β with IC_{50} values in a sub- μ M range. Nowadays, inhibitors of this enzyme are considered as attractive targets to evolve antidiabetic agents^{60,61}.

Figure 22. Benzocoumarin-based products with antidiabetic potential as depicted by Imhoff et al.

Recently, Kumar and his colleagues have synthesized and evaluated the antidiabetic potential of a new series of coumarin-cycloimide derivatives. Two of these derivatives, **S86** and **S87**, were based on a benzocoumarin moiety, as demonstrated in Figure 23. Both compounds revealed a moderate percentage of glucose-uptake activity via insulin-resistant cell model (HepG2) in values of 71.00 and 65.80%, respectively, at 50 nM, besides possessing a good safety profile⁶².

Figure 23. Benzocoumarin-based compounds with antidiabetic potential synthesized by Kumar et al.

Conclusion

Over the past decades, there has been a rising interest for benzocoumarins in medicinal chemistry, due primarily to their extended π -conjugation system compared to coumarins. This property has piqued experts' attention in investigating their biologically active aspects. Consequently, many natural and synthesized benzocoumarin derivatives were discovered to have a variety of bioactivities, such as antidiabetic, antimicrobial, anti-dyslipidemia, antitumor, and antioxidant effects. This review concluded that the benzocoumarin derivatives are potential scaffolds for drug candidates due to their characteristic pharmacological attributes. Thus, the research communities should put more effort into designing and synthesizing new benzocoumarins with novel or improved activities, besides learning more about these compounds' binding and mechanism of action with their targets.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

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References

1. Annunziata F, Pinna C, Dallavalle S, et al. An overview of coumarin as a versatile and readily accessible scaffold with broad-ranging biological activities. *Int J Mol Sci* 2020;21:1–83.
2. Mustafa YF, Khalil R, Mohammed T, et al. Effects of structural manipulation on the bioactivity of some coumarin-based products. *Arch Razi Inst* 2021;76:1297–1305.
3. Mustafa YF, Abdulaziza NT, Jasim MH. 4-Methylumbelliferone and its derived compounds: A brief review of their cytotoxicity. *Egypt J Chem* 2021;64:1807–1816.
4. Mustafa YF, Mohammed NAA. A promising oral 5-fluorouracil prodrug for lung tumor: Synthesis, characterization and release. *Biochem Cell Arch* 2021;21:1991–1999.
5. Mustafa YF, Khalil RR, Mohammed ET. Synthesis and antitumor potential of new 7-halocoumarin-4-acetic acid derivatives. *Egypt J Chem* 2021;64:3711–3716.
6. Bshir MK, Mustafa YF, Oglah MK. Synthesis and antitumor activity of new multifunctional coumarins. *Period Tche Quim* 2020;17:871–883.
7. Mustafa YF, Abdulaziz NT. Hymecromone and its products as cytotoxic candidates for brain cancer: A brief review. *NeuroQuantology* 2021;19:175–186.
8. Bashir MK, Mustafa YF, Oglah MK. Antitumor, antioxidant, and antibacterial activities of glycosyl-conjugated compounds: A review. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:175–187.
9. Kamalova FM, Sharapova OV, Gerasimova LI, et al. Analysis of territorial and age features of morbidity and availability of medical care. *Arch Venez Farmacol y Ter* 2021;40:748–752.
10. Oglah MK, Bashir MK, Mustafa YF, et al. Synthesis and biological activities of 3,5-disubstituted-4-hydroxycinnamic acids linked to a functionalized coumarin. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:717–725.
11. Mustafa YF, Mohammed ET, Khalil RR. Antioxidant and antitumor activities of methanolic extracts obtained from Red delicious and Granny Smith apples' seeds. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:570–576.
12. Oglah MK, Mustafa YF. Synthesis, antioxidant, and preliminary antitumor activities of new curcumin analogues. *J Glob Pharma Technol* 2020;12:854–862.
13. Torrenegra-Alarcón M, Ortega-Toro R, Herrera-Barros A. Recent advances in the use of nanomaterials with antimicrobial capacity. *Arch Venez Farmacol y Ter* 2020;39:986–992.
14. Mustafa YF, Bashir MK, Oglah MK, et al. Bioactivity of some natural and semisynthetic coumarin derived compounds. *NeuroQuantology* 2021;19:129–138.
15. Mustafa YF, Kasim SM, Al-Dabbagh BM, et al. Synthesis, characterization and biological evaluation of new azo-coumarinic derivatives. *Appl Nanosci* 2021. doi:10.1007/s13204-021-01873-w.
16. Mustafa YF, Khalil RR, Mohammed ET. Antimicrobial activity of aqueous extracts acquired from the seeds of two apples' cultivars. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:382–387.
17. Mustafa YF, Oglah MK, Bashir MK. Conjugation of sinapic acid analogues with 5-Fluorouracil: Synthesis, preliminary cytotoxicity, and release study. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:482–489.
18. Mustafa YF, Mohammed ET, Khalil RR. Synthesis, characterization, and anticoagulant activity of new functionalized biscoumarins. *Egypt J Chem* 2021;64:4461–4468.

19. Mustafa YF, Abdulaziz NT. Biological potentials of hymecromone-based derivatives: A systematic review. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:438–452.
20. Paredes FXP, Enríquez EAE, Peralvo MAN. Safety and immunogenicity of vaccines against SARS-CoV-2. *Arch Venez Farmacol y Ter* 2021;40:946–952.
21. Aldewachi H, Mustafa YF, Najm R, et al. Adulteration of slimming products and its detection methods. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:289–296.
22. Vellakkaran M, Hong S. Visible-light-induced reactions driven by photochemical activity of quinolinone and coumarin scaffolds. *Asian J Org Chem* 2021;10:1012–1023.
23. Kumar N, Udayabhanu, Alghamdi AA, et al. Solvent free and green synthesis of efficient solvchromism based coumarin moieties for quick visualization of LFPs and OLEDs applications. *J Mol Struct* 2021;1223:129208.
24. Gümüş M. Synthesis and characterization of novel hybrid compounds containing coumarin and benzodiazepine rings based on dye. *J Heterocycl Chem* 2021;58:1943–1954.
25. Russo M, Rigano F, Arigò A, et al. Coumarins, psoralens and polymethoxyflavones in cold-pressed citrus essential oils: A review. *J Essent Oil Res* 2021;33:221–239.
26. Mustafa YF. Classical approaches and their creative advances in the synthesis of coumarins: A brief review. *J Med Chem Sci* 2021;4:612–625.
27. Jung Y, Jung J, Huh Y, et al. Benzo[g]coumarin-Based Fluorescent Probes for Bioimaging Applications. *J Anal Methods Chem* 2018;2018. doi:10.1155/2018/5249765.
28. Lv H, Tu P, Jiang Y. Benzocoumarins: Isolation, synthesis, and biological activities. *Mini-Reviews Med Chem* 2014;14:603–622.
29. Bhatia R, Pathania S, Singh V, et al. Metal-catalyzed synthetic strategies toward coumarin derivatives. *Chem Heterocycl Compd* 2018;54:280–291.
30. Mustafa YF, Bashir MK, Oglah MK. Original and innovative advances in the synthetic schemes of coumarin-based derivatives: A review. *Syst Rev Pharm* 2020;11:598–612.
31. Lončarić M, Sokač DG, Jokić S, et al. Recent advances in the synthesis of coumarin derivatives from different starting materials. *Biomolecules* 2020;10:1–36.
32. Kim D, Xuan QP, Moon H, et al. Synthesis of benzocoumarins and characterization of their photophysical properties. *Asian J Org Chem* 2014;3:1089–1096.
33. Tasiar M, Kim D, Singha S, et al. π -Expanded coumarins: Synthesis, optical properties and applications. *J Mater Chem C* 2015;3:1421–1446.
34. Boutin R, Koh S, Tam W. Recent advances in transition metal-catalyzed reactions of oxabenzonorbornadiene. *Curr Org Synth* 2018;16:460–484.
35. Alfei S, Marengo B, Zuccari G. Oxidative stress, antioxidant capabilities, and bioavailability: Ellagic acid or urolithins? *Antioxidants* 2020;9:1–34.
36. Hekal MH, Abu El-Azm FSM, Samir SS. An efficient approach for the synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of some new benzocoumarins and related compounds. *Synth Commun* 2021;51:2175–2186.
37. Jaber QAH, Abdul-Rida NA, Adnan S. Boosting 3H-benzo[f]chromen-3-one chalcone with anti-inflammatory drugs: Synthesis, characterization, and evaluation of cytotoxicity and antimicrobial activity. *Russ J Org Chem* 2020;56:1622–1627.
38. Zhang H, Huang W, Song Y, et al. Four 6H-dibenzo[b,d]pyran-6-one derivatives produced by the endophyte *Cephalosporium acremonium* IFB-E007. *Helv Chim Acta* 2005;88:2861–2864.
39. Pratap R, Ram VJ. Natural and synthetic chromenes, fused chromenes, and versatility of dihydrobenzo[h]chromenes in organic synthesis. *Chem Rev* 2014;114:10476–10526.
40. Seo EK, Wani MC, Wall ME, et al. New bioactive aromatic compounds from *Vismia guianensis*. *Phytochemistry* 2000;55:35–42.
41. Wang X, Bastow KF, Sun C-M, et al. Antitumor agents. 239. Isolation, structure elucidation, total synthesis, and anti-breast cancer activity of neo-tanshinlactone from *Salvia miltiorrhiza*. *J Med Chem* 2004;47:5816–5819.
42. Wang X, Nakagawa-Goto K, Bastow KF, et al. Antitumor agents. 254. Synthesis and biological evaluation of novel neo-tanshinlactone analogues as potent anti-breast cancer agents. *J Med Chem* 2006;49:5631–5634.
43. Dong Y, Shi Q, Pai HC, et al. Antitumor agents. 272. Structure-activity relationships and in vivo selective anti-breast cancer activity of novel neo-tanshinlactone analogues. *J Med Chem* 2010;53:2299–2308.
44. Dong Y, Nakagawa-Goto K, Lai CY, et al. Antitumor agents 278. 4-Amino-2H-benzo[h]chromen-2-one (ABO) analogs as potent in vitro anti-cancer agents. *Bioorganic Med Chem Lett* 2010;20:4085–4087.
45. Dong Y, Nakagawa-Goto K, Lai C, et al. Antitumor agents. 289. Design, synthesis, and anti-breast cancer activity in vivo of 4-amino-2H-benzo[h]chromen-2-one and 4-amino-7,8,9,10-tetrahydro-2H-benzo[h]chromen-2-one analogues with improved water solubility. *J Nat Prod* 2012;75:370–377.
46. Sashidhara K V., Rosaiah JN, Kumar M, et al. Neo-tanshinlactone inspired synthesis, in vitro evaluation of novel substituted benzocoumarin derivatives as potent anti-breast cancer agents. *Bioorganic Med Chem Lett* 2010;20:7127–7131.
47. Abdul-Ridha NA, Salmaan AD, Sabah R, et al. Synthesis, cytotoxicity and in silico study of some novel benzocoumarin-chalcone-bearing aryl ester derivatives and benzocoumarin-derived arylamide analogs. *Zeitschrift für Naturforsch B* 2021;76:201–210.
48. Song YC, Huang WY, Sun C, et al. Characterization of graphislactone A as the antioxidant and free radical-scavenging substance from the culture of *Cephalosporium* sp. IFB-E001, an endophytic fungus in *Trachelospermum jasminoides*. *Biol Pharm Bull* 2005;28:506–509.
49. Djedjibegovic J, Marjanovic A, Panieri E, et al. Ellagic acid-derived urolithins as modulators of oxidative stress. *Oxid Med Cell Longev* 2020;2020:5194508.
50. Sashidhara K V., Rosaiah JN, Bhatia G, et al. Novel keto-enamine Schiff's bases from 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-benzo[h]chromene-8,10-dicarbaldehyde as potential antidyslipidemic and antioxidant agents. *Eur J Med Chem* 2008;43:2592–2596.
51. Salem MAI, Marzouk MI, El-Kazak AM. Synthesis and characterization of some new coumarins with in vitro antitumor and antioxidant activity and high protective effects against DNA damage. *Molecules* 2016;21:249–269.
52. Kim N, Sohn MJ, Kim CJ, et al. Verrulactones A and B, new

inhibitors of *Staphylococcus aureus* enoyl-ACP reductase produced by *Penicillium verruculosum* F375. *Bioorganic Med Chem Lett* 2012;22:2503–2506.

53. Zaki RM, Elossaily YA, Kamal El-Dean AM. Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of novel benzo[f]coumarin compounds. *Russ J Bioorganic Chem* 2012;38:639–646.
54. Zhou XM, Zhang B, Chen GY, et al. Dendrocoumarin: A new benzocoumarin derivative from the stem of *Dendrobium nobile*. *Nat Prod Res* 2018;32:2464–2467.
55. Patel M, Patel K. Naphthalene substituted benzo[c]coumarins: Synthesis, characterization and evaluation of antibacterial activity and cytotoxicity. *Heterocycl Commun* 2019;25:146–151.
56. Tang W, Xu H, Zeng D, et al. The antifungal constituents from the seeds of *Itoa orientalis*. *Fitoterapia* 2012;83:513–517.
57. Nabeel AAR, Adnan S, Jaber QAH. Development of novel imaging fluorescent agents bearing anti-inflammatory drugs: Synthesis, structural characterization and evaluation of biological activity. *Russ J Bioorganic Chem* 2020;46:620–626.
58. Sharma R, Soman S. Design, synthesis and preliminary evaluation of 3-aminocoumarin derivatives as DDP-IV inhibitor. *pharmanest* 2015;6:2679–2684.
59. Naveed MA, Riaz N, Saleem M, et al. New enzyme inhibitory constituents from *Tribulus longipetalus*. *Rec Nat Prod* 2016;10:128–136.
60. Wiese J, Imhoff JF, Gulder TAM, et al. Marine fungi as producers of benzocoumarins, a new class of inhibitors of glycogen-synthase-kinase 3 β . *Mar Drugs* 2016;14:1–9.
61. Golubev IV, Gureev VV, Korokina LV, et al. The anti-aggregation activity of new 11-amino acid of erythropoietin derivate containing tripeptide motifs. *Arch Venez Farmacol y Ter* 2020;39:588–591.
62. Reddy DS, Kongot M, Singh V, et al. Coumarin tethered cyclic imides as efficacious glucose uptake agents and investigation of hit candidate to probe its binding mechanism with human serum albumin. *Bioorg Chem* 2019;92:103212.